

Identity Theft: Trends, Detection and Prevention

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Abstract— The topic of this paper is identity theft. In this paper, I will discuss the types of identity theft, techniques in how identity theft occurs, the trends in identity theft, how to detect identity theft, and how to prevent identity theft. I will conclude this paper with my reflection on identity theft.

Keywords— Identity theft, identity fraud, identity abuse, cybercrime

I. INTRODUCTION

Identity theft, also known as identity fraud and identity abuse, is a major issue that is impacting society. Identity theft is commonly seen as a “gateway” crime; this act is used as a tool and is performed as a foundation to execute further unlawful acts such as creating stolen or fraudulent identities to steal money, claiming eligibility for services, or seeking unauthorised access to networks [1]. With the developments made in the IT sector, information has progressed to become a valuable asset and therefore hackers are seeking sensitive information from organisations and individuals for personal gain [2].

Identity thefts are categorised into two groups; true name identity theft and account take over identity theft. True name identity theft is when a perpetrator uses stolen personal information to open new accounts. The perpetrator could open a new credit card account or use an individual’s personal details for services.

Account take over identity theft is when a perpetrator uses an individual’s personal information to obtain their existing accounts. A common practice of this is changing the mailing address of a victims account and exploiting it before the victim is made aware of this theft. [3].

II. TYPES OF IDENTITY THEFT

- Financial Identity Theft - This is the most common identity theft and occurs when someone expropriates a person’s name, social security number, or other personal information to perform unlawful acts [4]. An attacker could use this to take out loans, attain services, and make purchases. Attackers can use the victims personal information to create a new bank account and then exploit or use their existing bank account.
- Medical Identity Theft - This type of identity theft is where an attacker abuses a person’s medical service [4]. The attacker can use this service to connect to the medical services and could potentially execute insurance fraud.
- Synthetic identity theft - This theft is when a perpetrator produces credible but false identity. This is unchallenging to create however it is difficult to illustrate it as plausible [5]. For example, the perpetrator may use a true national insurance number and combine it with false information such as name, date of birth, and address.
- Tax identity theft - This type of theft is when a perpetrator uses a victims national insurance number to illegally file a tax return and claim a refund [6]. This will impact the victim as they will experience difficulties when applying for a tax refund as the perpetrator will previously have taken the tax refund.
- Criminal identity theft - This is when a criminal uses the stolen details of another person when dealing with law authorities. For example, a criminal may provide the details of another person when facing driving points; the points will then be sent to the victim who will either not be aware of the crime or will face issues when they are made aware of the incident [24].
- Identity cloning and concealment - In this case the perpetrator is using another individuals identity so that they can keep their own identity confidential [7]. The primary motive is to commit a crime however this theft can be used for the sole purpose to keep their own identity discreet for personal reasons.

III. IDENTITY THEFT TECHNIQUES

Identity theft techniques and are categorised into one of two categories; technological identity theft and non-technological identity theft.

Non-Technological theft

- Physical theft - The oldest form of identity theft is the physical stealing of a individual’s belongings such as wallet or purse. A perpetrator is usually able to attain a significant amount of data as the majority of the population have bank cards and drivers licenses in their wallet or purse. Therefore, limiting the amount of personal information that is carried will reduce the size of exploitation if the scenario arises.
- Dumpster diving - This is where a perpetrator will seek through your rubbish to find sensitive information such as bank, bills, and phone statements. This illustrates the lengths a perpetrator will go to seek personal information [8].
- Social engineering - This is the practice whereby a perpetrator will deceive an individual for sensitive information via a range of mediums including person, telephone, or computer [25,26]. This method is highly successful because the perpetrator will usually have some prior knowledge on the individual and will use this to present themselves as legitimate and seek personal information [9].

Technological Theft

- Spamming and phishing – This is used to cheat users for their confidential details. This is the digital version of social engineering. Identity thieves will send unsought emails and portray themselves as legitimate institutions such as banks, or government. They will request sensitive information such as their credit card numbers or passwords. Furthermore, identity thieves can lure victims using the technique typosquatting which is performed when the victim is asked to use an infected website which is similar to the legitimate website portrayed [10].
- Keyloggers - Identity thieves can use the technique of installing hardware keyloggers between a keyboard and computer on public computers such as libraries. This is a technique that monitors users keystrokes and will communicate the keystrokes to the perpetrator. Identity thieves will use this method to obtain fraudulent access to usernames, passwords and other sensitive information [10].
- SQL Injection Attack - A successful technological identity theft was the SQL injection attack that occurred in 2010. This was the biggest application vulnerability used to access online data. This attack was performed through injecting SQL into the application fields to study the responses of the system. This technique was used to attack databases that stores personal information of users. This technique allowed the perpetrator, Albert Gonzales, to exploit upwards of 130 million credit card numbers from five financial companies and stores [11].

IV. TRENDS

Identity theft has been around for the past few decades and is a growing cybercrime that is progressing in parallel with technological advancements. In today's age, cybercriminals have the platform and the tools necessary to perform malicious attacks and therefore are introducing more complex and sophisticated fraudulent schemes [28]. For example, with the technological advancements in managing financial accounts increasing, identity thieves are developing greater types of attacks.

Identity theft which was first introduced as being physical such as the thieving of wallets to seek bank cards and identification information; it has now developed into the digital world. Cybersecurity firm, Risk Based Security, highlight that since 2010, more than 38 billion records have been breached of their data. Furthermore, the cyber security firm also portray that there are many sensitive data records that are already in the hands of perpetrators and can exploit them as they please [12]. Therefore, it is very important that individuals and businesses are ensuring that they are keeping up with the latest trends in security attacks and defenses.

Most of today's society have access to computers and online platforms which they use daily. Activities such as online banking and online shopping. Performing tasks online such as online payments is presenting an individual to become more prone to digital fraud in comparison to in store cash purchases.

The graph above illustrates the top three most identity theft reports between the years 2014 – 2018 [13]. As illustrated above, credit card fraud is on the rise and this is a reflection of the changes in modern day society. One significant change that has been pushed in this time frame is the online shopping service. Online shopping providers are attracting customers by offering customers free home delivery and returns. This is therefore increasing the number of users performing card transactions and therefore opening the window of opportunity for identity fraud via user's credit card credentials. Security principles have been implemented such as the use of banking apps to confirm online transactions.

One of the most common and frequently used identity theft method in the past six months is the use of Experian, Equifax and other credit monitoring accounts. Perpetrators use this tool to seek credit reports for forgotten accounts or credit cards and exploit them [12]. For example, a perpetrator will find an individual's credit card that has not been used and will request a new card to be provided at a false address. The replacement card will then be available to the perpetrator to perform fraudulent activity.

The general population in our society believe that identity theft consists of only online shopping and credit card fraud however this is a recent development in identity theft. Ballot stuffing and voter fraud is one of the most common and oldest identity theft that has existed [30]. This identity theft was constructed of a perpetrator using the identity of another individual or creating a false identity for the purpose of increasing the number of votes for the specific party [14]. During the 2019 UK voting, there were 595 incidents of this identity theft reported and investigated by the police [15]. This illustrates that although this is an old technique, it is still frequently used in today's society.

Since the introduction of a minimum age to participate in activities such as purchasing alcohol, cigarettes, and accessing certain environments, the number of false identities produced have soared. False identity cards are commonly available in the UK and the companies that produce these are often foreign based. Consequently, preventing the UK from restricting the supply of these items. However, there are UK Acts implemented to deter people from producing and using false identity cards. Moreover, in this practice it is more common to see genuine ID cards used which do not belong to the individual using it [16].

Identity theft has increased by 11% in the first six months of 2021 according to the UK's National Fraud Database. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, criminals are taking advantage of the recovering economy and incidents are looking to surge into 2022 [17]. Identity theft is continuing to rise due to more of society moving towards a digital environment. This has been strengthened due to the lockdowns that have been implemented which have restricted physical interaction [31]. This ranges from education being delivered via video conferencing platforms such as Zoom, to medical consultations being conducted via pictures and calls. The window of opportunity for identity theft is bigger than ever before.

V. DETECTION

Identity theft is one of the most common cybercrimes and therefore it is important to be able to detect identity theft activity early and consequently prevent or reduce the impact. In most cases, it is the victim who is the first to discover the attack.

Below are some common warning signs that can inform you if you are a victim of identity theft.

- Missing documents - Important personal documents, such as passports or driver's licenses, should not be misplaced as these hold significant personal information and if they are to come into the wrong hands then the perpetrator is easily able to take out a loan, credit, or perform other tasks with the information. Mail theft is a source of missing documents. If you are expecting mail and it does not arrive, then this could portray that the mail is being directed elsewhere and is being used seek personal information or using the individual details for other unlawful activities such as placing orders using the victim's details but using an alternative address.
- Unrecognised items - It is important to monitor your bank account regularly as even a small discrepancy on an individual's bank account can illustrate that they are a victim of identity theft [18]. If any transactions are unrecognised then it is important to contact the bank or credit card provider and raise this issue and follow the services protocols. A widely used protocol is the locking of the account which will prevent future unauthorised transactions to take place. Furthermore, requesting replacement bank account details, such as account number, would assist in the prevention of unauthorised access as the previous details will no longer be valid and therefore preventing the perpetrator access.

- Credit score - If an individual notices their credit score is going down and do not understand the reasoning to why it may have dropped then they could be a victim of identity theft. Perpetrators may have used their details to take out a loan or credit [33]. Similarly, if the credit score of an individual is rising and they have not done anything to reflect the growing score then this could potentially be done to extend credit in the individuals name before exploiting it.
- Warrant for arrest - If a perpetrator has personal information on an individual such as their name, date of birth, and address, then they can provide these to the law authorities such as the police when being challenged with criminal activity. This is known as criminal identity theft and the victim will need to illustrate their innocence as well as providing supporting evidence to who they are.
- Law enforcement contact - If an individual is receiving calls or letters from debt collectors or solicitors regarding debt that the individual does not recognise then this illustrates that the individual has been the victim of identity theft. The perpetrator has placed debt in the individuals name and as a result the victim is being faced with law enforcements.

VI. PREVENTION

With the importance of information growing and individuals moving towards a digital society, the hunger for perpetrators to abuse the information is expanding. The introduction of the intranet and cloud computing has allowed perpetrators greater access to information and consequently have simulated individuals and organisations to review security more rigorously [19]. It is now more important than ever before to ensure we are safe from identity theft.

- Safeguard physical personal details - It is important to ensure that the security of your personal details are competent. When disposing personal information, it is important that you dispose of it correctly and safely [20]. Disposing information through a recycling bin allows a perpetrator to seek this information. However, if the personal information is destroyed via shredding, then this would eliminate the possibility of the personal details being retrieved.
- Beware of phishing and spoofing - Criminals use phishing and spoofing to seek an individual's details, they will present themselves as trustworthy by acting on behalf of their bank, government, or a business. They will use any method that will present themselves as legitimate and once an individual has been lured they will then be exploited and use their details for identity fraud. An individual can ensure that they are not being a victim of this act by initiating a callback or return email to the contact party. It is advised to return the communication method using a known entity such as the party's official website or number.

- Passwords - When creating passwords for the various accounts and platforms, it is important that an individual creates a password that is unique, complex, and different. It is important to have a unique and complex password so that it cannot be easily obtained by a perpetrator. Strong passwords implement a mixture of lowercase and uppercase characters, special characters, and numbers, or create passphrases which are not of the norm but easy for the user to remember [21]. An individual should have different passwords for each account they use because if one account password is exploited then it is very easy for perpetrators to attack all the victims accounts. To further strengthen the use of passwords, users should change them regularly. This can help reduce the risk of being a victim of identity theft and moreover can help stop further identity theft occurring on accounts where the password has been exposed [34]. It is strongly advised that all devices which hold personal data should be locked and protected with a password. Further security can be implemented using biometric requests as this is more complex for perpetrators to overcome.
- Secure devices - Citizens of modern day society are increasingly relying upon digital services to assist in their day to day activities. These activities include banking, online purchases, and sharing personal information over social networking platforms. This has led to a shift in attention for identity theft perpetrators to exploit individuals on these platforms. To avoid being a victim of this, it is essential users implement device locks, encrypting data stored on devices, avoid using public Wi-Fi or VPN, and install anti-virus software. Norton and McAfee are two of the most renowned anti-virus software and it is important to keep up to date with the latest versions and updates. It is good practice to enable automatic updates to ensure you are always protected from cybercriminals.

VII. CONCLUSION

Identity theft is arguably the most dangerous cybercrime; the damage and effect that it brings can be exponential. It is important for individuals and organisations to be safe and prepared against identity theft attacks such as data breaches which are out of our control. Security companies are trying to keep users safe from identity thieves, but they cannot always countermand the attacks and therefore relying on them alone is not sufficient. Being always vigilant against identity thieves is difficult but keeping up to date with identity theft types, the techniques used, the trends, how they can detect, and ultimately how they can prevent can assist in reducing the risk of them falling victim. In many scenarios, the victim of identity theft is unaware and lacks the knowledge in the situation. It is important to be educated on identity theft because we unfortunately live in a society where identity theft is increasing, and no individual or organisation is safe from exploitation. Introducing public awareness campaign and educating the public would make it difficult for identity thieves to attack and therefore decline number of identity theft cases.

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